

Radiation exposure in low Earth orbit measured with the RAMIS instrument on the DLR Eu:CROPIS satellite

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Key points:

- The RAMIS instrument is a silicon telescope measuring energy deposition spectra, absorbed dose and dose equivalent of cosmic radiation.
- RAMIS has been flying on the DLR Eu:CROPIS satellite since 2018 in a low Earth orbit and has been providing data on galactic cosmic radiation, radiation belt particles and solar energetic particles ever since.
- Energy deposition spectra measured by RAMIS can be used to estimate the linear energy spectra of cosmic radiation and their biological relevance through the quality factor of the field.

Keywords: radiation exposure; galactic cosmic radiation; solar energetic particles; radiation belts; low Earth orbit.

Abstract – The radiation environment in space and the related radiation exposure is seen as one of the main health detriments for human missions in and beyond low Earth orbit (LEO). In addition to national space agencies sending astronauts to space, the near future is likely to bring numerous commercial endeavours that will facilitate the access to space, and specifically to LEO, for a growing number of people. The components of the cosmic radiation forming the environment in LEO are the galactic cosmic radiation (GCR), inner and outer radiation belt particles and sporadic solar energetic particle events. The steady flux of energetic particles in the galactic cosmic radiation produces a chronic low-dose-rate exposure, which is heavily influenced by several factors including variations during the solar cycle, the Earth's magnetic field and spacecraft shielding. Investigations of the GCR variations over the course of a solar cycle provide valuable data for exploration mission planning and for the determination of the radiation load received due to the GCR environment. The RAMIS (Radiation Measurement in Space) instrument onboard the DLR Eu:CROPIS satellite, named after its primary payload: Euglena and Combined Regenerative Organic-Food Production in Space, has been measuring the radiation environment in a sun-synchronous polar orbit at 500 km to 600 km altitude since December 2018 and has been providing data on the exposure from GCR, inner and outer radiation belt particles and during numerous solar energetic particle events. Measurements at high latitudes and low geomagnetic shielding provide information on the exposure outside the magnetosphere in near-Earth interplanetary space.

45 1. Introduction

46 The space radiation environment and its impact on humans have been seen as one of
47 the main challenges for long duration human space missions. This is of particular importance
48 for future exploration missions to the Moon, to near Earth asteroids and to Mars (Durante &
49 Cucinotta, 2011) but also for the growing interest and endeavours of commercial spaceflight
50 in Low Earth Orbit (LEO), that will likely provide the opportunity to visit space to more and
51 more people. The radiation environment in space is composed of galactic cosmic radiation
52 (GCR), which – modulated by solar activity – is the cause of the omnipresent background
53 radiation in space. For long duration missions GCR will be the primary source of stochastic
54 radiation effects resulting in additional risk of exposure induced cancer (Cucinotta et al., 2017;
55 Cucinotta & Pak, 2024; ICRP, 2013; NCRP, 2014). The GCR environment is influenced by
56 various parameters, the main driver of changes in the GCR environment in free space is the
57 Sun due to the 11-year solar cycle, which causes variations in the strength and structure of the
58 interplanetary magnetic field. This solar modulation leads to the highest GCR intensities during
59 solar minimum, when the magnetic field is weakest, and the lowest intensities during solar
60 maximum conditions, when the magnetic field is strongest. The variations of GCR have been
61 measured indirectly on Earth for several decades using the neutron monitor network (data of
62 many stations is available at <https://nmdb.eu/>).

63 Another source of radiation are high-energy particles, mainly protons, that are
64 accelerated during solar particle events (SPEs) (Cucinotta & Pak, 2024; Kim et al., 2017).
65 Astronauts on board the International Space Station (ISS) are protected against high doses from
66 these solar energetic particles as a result of being shielded by the geomagnetic field for much
67 of its trajectory. This will not be the case for trajectories in free space or on the surface of
68 planetary bodies without a magnetic field and/or substantial atmosphere, such as the Moon and
69 Mars.

70 Compared to the relatively stable and only slowly changing GCR exposure in
71 interplanetary space, the situation is different for LEO due to the fact that the Earth's magnetic
72 field provides an effective protection mechanism against charged particles which leads to a
73 strong dependence of the GCR dose rates on latitude and longitude or more specifically on the
74 magnitude of the geomagnetic shielding. In addition to the continuous GCR background and
75 sporadic solar energetic particle events, spacecraft and astronauts in LEO are also exposed to
76 radiation from the inner and outer radiation belt (Li & Hudson, 2019). Spacecraft in LEO cross
77 the inner radiation belt in the south Atlantic anomaly (SAA) and the outer radiation belt at
78 higher latitudes. The contribution and the variation of the different particle populations within
79 the ISS have been extensively measured in the past, e.g. (Badavi et al., 2011; Benghin et al.,
80 2023; Berger et al., 2013; Berger et al., 2017; Dachev, 2018; Di Fino et al., 2023; Gaza et al.,
81 2023; Jadrníčková et al., 2009; Kroupa et al., 2023; Labrenz et al., 2015; Matthiä et al., 2023;
82 Semkova et al., 2010; Semkova et al., 2014; Stoffle et al., 2023; Zeitlin et al., 2023) and
83 references therein. Due to its low inclination of 51.6°, however, the ISS avoids most of the
84 regions of very low geomagnetic shielding and only grazes the regions where the outer
85 radiation belt particles are reaching LEO. Additionally, most measurements on the ISS have
86 been performed inside the station at locations of heavy mass shielding, which reduces the
87 sensitivity to lower energetic particles. Thus, detectors on satellites on polar orbits and under
88 low shielding conditions can provide insights into the physical processes acting at lower
89 energies (Botek et al., 2023; Cyamukungu et al., 2014; Evans et al., 2008; Gieseler et al., 2020;
90 Gohl et al., 2023; Granja et al., 2016; Pierrard et al., 2020; Sandberg et al., 2011; Siegl et al.,
91 2010).

92 Within this work we present an overview of the Radiation Measurement in Space
93 (RAMIS) instrument developed and operated by the German Aerospace Center (DLR), that

94 has been flying since December 2018 on the DLR Eu:CROPIS satellite. RAMIS has been
 95 measuring the dose, dose equivalent, energy deposition spectra and the linear energy transfer
 96 (*LET*) spectra under low shielding conditions in the satellite's sun-synchronous polar orbit at
 97 around 500 to 600 km altitude, where distinct particle populations from the galactic cosmic
 98 radiation, the inner and outer radiation belt and sporadic solar energetic particle events could
 99 be observed.

100 2. Eu:CROPIS and RAMIS

101 2.1. The Eu:CROPIS satellite

102 The Eu:CROPIS satellite (Budroweit & Drobczyk, 2019; Delovski et al., 2019; Drobczyk &
 103 Budroweit, 2017, 2020; Hauslage et al., 2018; Orłowski-Feldhusen et al., 2020; Pedersen,
 104 2017) is a spin stabilized satellite and has a cylindrical shape with a wet mass of 234 kg. It is
 105 powered by four solar arrays and has dimensions of 1.1 x 1.1 x 1.1 m³ as long as the solar
 106 arrays are not deployed and of 2.9 x 2.9 x 1.1 m³ after solar array deployment. Eu:CROPIS
 107 was launched on 3 December 2018 at 18:34:05 UTC by a SpaceX Falcon 9 rocket from
 108 Vandenberg Air Force Base, California, USA and injected into a sun-synchronous orbit of 574
 109 km altitude and a 98° inclination.

110
 111 **Figure 1: The top of the Eu:CROPIS satellite with the RAMIS instrument in its aluminium housing indicated by the**
 112 **red arrow; the inset shows the detector's interior, electronics and the silicon telescope on the left. The silicon telescope**
 113 **is covered by 3 mm Al during operation.**

114 Figure 1 provides a picture of the top view of the Eu:CROPIS satellite in the clean room of the
 115 DLR-Institute of Space Systems in Bremen, Germany. RAMIS sits on the top of the satellite
 116 shown in the shiny aluminium case. The inset in Figure 1 provides a view inside RAMIS (top
 117 cover plate removed) and shows the digital board and in the upper left corner the silicon
 118 detector stack arranged in a telescope configuration. After the launch and early operations
 119 phase (Lino et al., 2021) Eu:CROPIS became fully functional and continuous data recording
 120 of RAMIS started on the 11 December 2018.

121 **2.2. The RAMIS Instrument**

122 The RAMIS instrument (Figure 1, top) is, similar to previous instruments (Ritter et al., 2014),
 123 based on two circular Passivated Implanted Planar Silicon detectors FD50-14-300RM
 124 (Canberra Industries, now Mirion Technologies). Table 1 provides detailed information on the
 125 detector and the diodes used within RAMIS. Its dimensions, voltage supply and power
 126 consumption are listed in Table 1, as well.

127 **Table 1 RAMIS flight model, single detector and telescope specifications**

RAMIS Flight Model			
Dimensions	140·140·35 mm ³		
Mass	608 g		
Supply voltage	28 V		
Current consumption	65 mA		
Power consumption	1.82 W		
Single Detector		Telescope	
area (A) ¹	0.817 cm ²	distance between the diodes	7.3 mm
thickness	300 μm	max. penetration angle ³	54.4°
diameter	10.20 mm	average penetration angle ³	25.6°
mass	57.1 mg	mean path length ³	335.8 μm
GF ²	5.13 sr·cm ²	GF ³	1.423 sr·cm ²

Notes:

¹The total active area of the FD50-14-300RM, relevant for high-energy ionizing radiation, exceeds the visible active area of 50 mm², which is given in the manufacturer's specification.

²The two-sided geometric factor given here for a planar detector is $2\pi A$ (one-sided: πA).

³These values are based on Monte Carlo calculations for 300 μm thick diodes. The analytic solution by Sullivan (1971) for a telescope with infinitesimally thin detectors is a geometric factor of 1.357 sr·cm².

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 129 The thickness of the single detectors is 300 μm and the sensitive area of each detector is
 130 81.7 mm² (diameter of 10.20 mm). For a 4π isotropic irradiation this yields a geometric factor
 131 (GF) of the single detector of 5.13 sr·cm² (Sullivan, 1971).

132 The two circular detectors are arranged parallel to each other at a distance of 7.3 mm in a
 133 telescope geometry; the upper detector of the telescope is called D1 and the lower D2. The
 134 measurement range for the energy deposition (E_{dep}) in silicon is 0.09 to 141 MeV. The detector
 135 also measures coincident hits in both detector planes to restrict the incidence angle of
 136 penetrating particles and thus the path length through the detectors. This allows to estimate the
 137 linear energy transfer of particles traversing the detector, which can then be used to derive the
 138 quality factor Q and to measure the dose equivalent. The maximum penetration angle of
 139 particles passing through both detectors of the telescope is approximately 54.4°, the geometry
 140 factor 1.423 sr·cm² (for a 4π irradiation) and the mean path length is 335.8 μm. The geometric
 141 factor (GF) was calculated using a Monte-Carlo approach and yields a slightly larger value
 142 than the analytic solution of 1.357 sr·cm² for two infinitesimally thin detectors in a telescope
 143 configuration (Sullivan, 1971). We use a factor of 1.23 to convert the dose in silicon to dose in
 144 water (Beaujean et al., 2002), and the conversion of the energy deposition in silicon to water
 145 can be derived as $1.23 \cdot \rho_{H_2O} / \rho_{Si} \approx 0.528$. Using the mean path length through the detector planes,
 146 the energy deposition in the individual detector in coincidence can be converted to lineal energy
 147 using a factor of $1.23 \cdot \rho_{H_2O} / \rho_{Si} / 335.8 \mu\text{m} \approx 1.57 \cdot 10^{-3} / \mu\text{m}$. Lineal energy is used as an
 148 approximation to linear energy transfer. With the thresholds for the energy deposition in
 149 silicon, the maximum LET range can be derived as 0.14 to 221 keV/μm.

150 The instrument is surrounded by an aluminium casing, that provides a 3 mm shielding against
 151 particles arriving perpendicular to the top surface of the casing. As a consequence, protons and

152 electrons require a minimum energy of 24.3 MeV and 1.38 MeV, respectively, to reach D1. To
 153 reach D2 particles need to additionally traverses the 0.3 mm of silicon of D1 and the minimum
 154 energy to reach this detector plane increases to 25.6 MeV for protons and 1.48 MeV for
 155 electrons. Particles penetrating the sides of the detector case need to traverse 4.3 mm of
 156 aluminium at minimum. The satellite provides a substantial amount of shielding against
 157 particles from below. The mass of the satellite (234 kg) and the projected area of a little less
 158 than one m² results in an approximate minimum shielding of about 25 g/cm², if a homogeneous
 159 mass distribution is assumed.

160

161 **Figure 2: RAMIS block diagram**

162 The overall block diagram of the instrument is depicted in Figure 2. The detectors have a
 163 thickness of 300 µm, full depletion voltage 30 V. Detector D1, located at the top of the
 164 telescope, and D2 below are operated under a reverse bias of 83.0 V, ensuring full silicon
 165 depletion. The charge signal is then amplified by charge sensitive amplifiers (CSA 1 and 2),
 166 utilizing A250 F/NF hybrid amplifiers (Amptek Inc., USA). Following signal processing
 167 encompasses shaping with a time constant of 1.5 µs.

168 To cover the wide dynamic range of deposited energies in silicon from 0.09 to 141 MeV, the
 169 signal is then split into two channels with different amplifications. The High Gain (HG) channel
 170 Amp 1A/Amp 2A covers a range up to 6 MeV, while the Low Gain (LG) Amp 1B/ Amp 2B
 171 measures deposited energies in silicon up to the maximum of 141 MeV.

172 Data acquisition is facilitated by analogue peak detectors PD 1A/B and PD 2A/B of type PH300
 173 (Amptek Inc.), followed by a 12-bit analogue to digital converter (ADC). Both diode HG
 174 channels are equipped with a discriminator/comparator (Comp 1 and 2) with user selectable
 175 threshold. When a signal pulse in any channel exceeds the threshold, the microcontroller (µC)
 176 triggers the analogue to digital conversion of all four peak detector voltages (PD 1A/B, PD
 177 2A/B). The resulting four digital values are stored to energy deposition spectra. Each diode
 178 D1/D2 and each amplification chain HG/LG has its own energy deposition spectra. Table 2

179 provides the range of the channel numbers used for the data evaluation and the respective
 180 thresholds in MeV. Note: These data reflect the on-orbit flight configuration of the system.

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182 **Table 2: Thresholds for the high gain and low gain channels of RAMIS.**

	D1	D2	
lower threshold high gain	channel #	16	17
	E_{dep}/MeV in Si	0.098	0.10
upper threshold high gain	channel #	949	939
	E_{dep}/MeV in Si	6.21	6.07
lower threshold low gain	channel #	47	46
	E_{dep}/MeV in Si	6.22	6.08
upper threshold low gain	channel #	1022	1022
	E_{dep}/MeV in Si	141	141

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184 Events detected in both diode channels D1 and D2 within a 3 μs time window are considered
 185 coincident events, and the digital values are stored in separate, so-called coincidence spectra.
 186 The microcontroller saves all spectra every 5 minutes to a radiation hardened external random-
 187 access memory (XMEM). A real-time clock (RTC) is used to timestamp the data. Temperature
 188 (TEMP) is measured at two distinct points within the unit and together with internally measured
 189 voltages this data forms part of the extended housekeeping engineering data. Command and
 190 data handling (C&DH) are conducted via the RS422 bus under the control of the onboard
 191 computer. The energy deposition verification and testing of the instrument was performed with
 192 radioactive sources and heavy ions at the Heavy Ion Medical Accelerator in Chiba (HIMAC)
 193 at NIRS/QST, Japan.

194 **2.2.1 RAMIS: Data Products**

195 Every five minutes RAMIS provides a data file to the Eu:CROPIS on-board computer (OBC)
 196 which consists of three subsets of data namely, the i) Housekeeping (H/K) data, ii) the Extended
 197 (EXT) H/K data and iii) the 5-minute spectral data, resulting in a total of 288 data files per day.
 198 The H/K data set comprises the RAMIS supply voltages for analogue and digital subsystems
 199 and the internal temperatures measured with two temperature sensors on the digital board of
 200 the system. This data is further used to check the stability of the hardware (voltages) and to
 201 provide an overall overview of the internal temperatures measured during the mission. The
 202 Extended H/K data provides the timestamp (end of integration time of the 5-minute spectrum
 203 data) as well as the cumulated doses and counts at 1-minute intervals within each 5-minute
 204 period for the D1 (top) detector of RAMIS. The cumulative dose is calculated and stored on-
 205 orbit based on the integrated energy deposition spectra each minute. The cumulative doses and
 206 counts are then used in the post-processing to calculate the dose rate at a 1-minute resolution.
 207 The third set are the energy deposition spectra measured with the D1 and the D2 detectors
 208 individually and in coincidence and for two different gains (high gain, low gain) of the
 209 amplifier chain. This corresponds to eight spectra with 1024 channels each, which are stored
 210 for every 5-minute time interval. The 5-minute data is used on ground to generate the combined
 211 (HG+LG) energy deposition spectra for each diode separately and in coincidence. The linear
 212 energy transfer spectra are derived from the energy deposition spectra measured in
 213 coincidence.

214 After processing the on-orbit data, RAMIS provides:

- 215 • 1-minute count rates and dose rates measured with the single D1 detector,
- 216 • 5-minute count rates and dose rates measured with the single D1 and D2 detectors,
- 217 • the coincidence (D1/D2) 5-minute count rates and dose rates

- 218 • energy deposition spectra for D1 and D2 separately and in coincidence in 5-minute
219 intervals
- 220 • and *LET* spectra in 5-minute intervals.

221 One additional (#289) data file is created every day shortly after midnight in RAMIS. This file
222 (Pulser File) is created by sending test pulses with three different amplitudes through the signal
223 chain of RAMIS. The test pulses generate entries in the eight energy deposition spectra of the
224 D1 and the D2 detector. These data are primarily used to check the long-term stability of the
225 electronics chain of the system. The creation of the pulser file takes below 1s and results in one
226 5-minute interval being less than 0.33% shorter than the other 287. This time difference is
227 neglected in the data analysis.

228 At the current time data from RAMIS is downlinked via the ground station at Weilheim in
229 Germany by GSOC (German Space Operations Center), once a week and then further
230 transferred to the MUSC (Microgravity User Support Center) and the science team at the
231 Institute of Aerospace Medicine for data evaluation.

232

233 3. Results

234 In the following we will provide an overview of measurements of the RAMIS
235 instrument on the Eu:CROPIS satellite mission. Dose rates shown in this section are dose rates
236 in water calculated from the values in silicon by multiplying with the conversion factor of 1.23.

237 3.1. Particle flux and dose rate along the trajectory

238 Eu:CROPIS performs 15 to 16 polar orbits per day and Figure 3 illustrates typical features of
239 the radiation field measured by RAMIS. One-minute-average particle flux (Figure 3a) and dose
240 rates (Figure 3b) measured on 28 October 2021 along the trajectory show the variations of the
241 radiation field in low Earth orbit caused by the different components of the field. The
242 omnipresent galactic cosmic radiation varies periodically over the orbit with two minima and
243 maxima in the dose rate and particle flux per orbit which are related to the maximum and
244 minimum magnetic shielding at low and high latitudes, respectively. The measured particle
245 flux and dose rate of GCR at this time close to solar minimum varied between approximately
246 $0.2 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $1 \text{ }\mu\text{Gy/h}$ at low latitudes and $2.5 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $15 \text{ }\mu\text{Gy/h}$ at high latitudes. By the
247 end of 2025 the maxima at high latitudes had dropped to approximately $1 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $6 \text{ }\mu\text{Gy/h}$.

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249 **Figure 3: Typical particle flux (a) and dose rate (b) measurements by RAMIS illustrated with data from 28 October**
 250 **2021. Periodic features like the variation of the GCR over the orbit and the inner radiation belt are complemented by**
 251 **sporadic contributions from the outer radiation belt and solar energetic particles.**

252 The passages of the inner radiation belt in the region of the South Atlantic Anomaly show up
 253 as distinct peaks in the flux and dose rates, where values of more than $1 \cdot 10^3 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and
 254 $1 \cdot 10^4 \mu\text{Gy/h}$ are reached. These peaks show up on the southern hemisphere on the decreasing
 255 or increasing flanks of the underlying GCR oscillations, depending on whether the satellite was
 256 north- or southbound at the time of the traversal and the maximum values in the peaks depend
 257 on how close the trajectory approaches the centre of the SAA.

258 During times of geomagnetic disturbances and related particle acceleration in the outer
 259 radiation belt, the particle intensity can temporarily increase and can be seen as additional
 260 contribution to the flux and dose rates. In Figure 3 these occur as small spikes on top of the
 261 periodic variation of the GCR. At that time, the flux of the outer radiation belt particles
 262 measured by RAMIS was low but during intense outer radiation belt events the flux values can
 263 exceed the flux in the inner radiation belt, for which examples are shown in the following.

264 Finally, the onset of the solar energetic particle event occurred at around 16:30 UTC on 28
 265 October 2021, when peak dose and count rates reached maximum values of about $55 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$
 266 and $580 \mu\text{Gy/h}$ and increased far above the pre-event GCR background. The contribution of
 267 the solar particles adds to the maxima of the GCR dose and flux rate, which occur during high
 268 latitude passes where the geomagnetic shielding is lowest. The event on the 28 October 2021
 269 was the first ground level enhancement of solar cycle 25 and one of the strongest events in
 270 recent years (Guo et al., 2023; Klein et al., 2022; Kouloumvakos et al., 2024; Mishev et al.,
 271 2022; Papaioannou et al., 2022).

272 3.2. Particle flux and dose rate versus L

273 The Eu:CROPIS satellite reaches on its polar orbit high values of L (McIlwain, 1961) and
 274 traverses both the inner and outer radiation belt. The L parameter is used to parameterize the
 275 bounce and drift shells of trapped charged particles in the radiation belts in units of multiples
 276 of the Earth's radius and is commonly used to describe radiation belt particle behaviour and to

277 separate the different particle populations. Figure 4 illustrates the contributions of these
 278 different particle populations to the particle flux (Figure 4a) and the dose rate (Figure 4b) on
 279 the 28 October 2021 in dependence of the L parameter. The values of L have been calculated
 280 with the PLANETOCOSMICS (Desorgher et al., 2006) application for Geant4 (Agostinelli et
 281 al., 2003; Allison et al., 2006; Allison et al., 2016) using the International Geomagnetic
 282 Reference Field (IGRF-14, Alken et al. (2021)) and Tsyganenko (1989). For this purpose, the
 283 source code of the PLANETOCOSMICS application was updated with the most recent IGRF
 284 coefficients.

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286 **Figure 4: Particle flux (a) and dose rate (b) versus L measured by RAMIS on 28 October 2021.**

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288 Dose rate and flux of charged particles from GCR extend from low L (~ 1.1) up to the highest
 289 values and show increasing values up to approximately $L \approx 4$. Contributions from particles in
 290 the inner radiation belt, that the satellite crosses in the SAA, show as a clear increase above the
 291 GCR at around $L \approx 1.3$ to 2.5. Particles in the outer radiation belt extend in this case from
 292 approximately $L \approx 3.5$ to 5 and solar energetic particles contribute above $L \approx 5$. A clear separation
 293 of the different particle populations is difficult and sometimes not even possible as they overlap
 294 in many cases. The GCR background contributes in any case.

295 Figure 5 summarizes the charged particle flux (Figure 5a) and dose rate (Figure 5b) measured
 296 by RAMIS since the launch in December 2018 in dependence on L . The figure illustrates the
 297 dynamic nature of the outer radiation belt, in which the particle flux and dose rate can vary
 298 over several orders of magnitude within hours and days, while the measurements in the inner
 299 radiation belt show a relatively stable flux and dose rate.

300

301 **Figure 5: One-day-averages of the particle flux (a) and the dose rate (b) versus L measured by RAMIS over the whole**
 302 **mission time so far. The geographical distribution of the particle flux in May 2020 (indicated as T_0), October 2021**
 303 **(T_1) and November 2021 (T_2) are illustrated in Figure 6.**

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3.3. Geographical distribution of particle flux

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The geographical distribution of different particle populations measured by RAMIS is illustrated in Figure 6 for the one-month-averages for May 2020, October 2021 and November 2021. May 2020 (Figure 6a) was selected as an example for a quiet month with almost no solar activity and no contributions from outer radiation belt particles, thereby showing only contributions of GCR and inner radiation belt particles in the SAA.

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The solar energetic particle event, that occurred on 28 October 2021 and that was already illustrated in Figure 3, led to increased flux values for individual orbital passes at high latitudes (Figure 6b). Additionally, typical features like the distribution of the contribution of the galactic cosmic radiation with low values at low latitudes and greater values at high latitudes are obvious. While the inner radiation belt in the SAA is clearly visible, the outer radiation belt hardly contributed to the measured particle flux in October 2021, probably due to the fact that the energies of most particles were below the threshold (1.38 MeV for electrons) to reach the detector through the minimum vertical shielding of 3 mm Al. Electron energies in the outer radiation belt are mostly below 1 MeV (Reeves et al., 2016).

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Following the October solar energetic particle event, a strong geomagnetic storm hit Earth leading to peak values of the Kp Index above 7 on 4 November 2021 (<https://kp.gfz.de/>). The geomagnetic disturbance led to the acceleration and population of the outer radiation belt with high energy particles that are visible as band structures in Figure 6c.

The range of the colour scale on Figure 6 was selected to visualize the distribution of the GCR, the regions of the inner and outer radiation belts, where the measured peak particle flux is much higher, and the solar energetic particles. Values above the scale appear in bright yellow. The identical data is shown in the annex (Figure A 1) with extended scale. The peak flux values in the one-minute-average data in the inner radiation belt reached $1.7 \cdot 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ during solar minimum and up to $7 \cdot 10^2 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in 2025. The particle flux in the outer radiation belt is very dynamic and the values are highest during and after geomagnetic storms. During the November

330 2021 event (Figure 6c) the measured peak flux in the outer radiation belt reached $1.2 \cdot 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
 331 $^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and during the strongest event measured by RAMIS to date in May 2024 the peak flux
 332 reached values of almost $3.8 \cdot 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

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Figure 6: Visualization of the geographical distribution of one-month-average particle fluence rates of different particle populations measured by RAMIS during solar quiet times in May 2020 (a), including a solar energetic particle event

336 in October 2021 (b) and the formation of a high-energy and high-intensity component in the outer radiation belt in
337 November 2021 (c). Note: the scale was limited to $20 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ to visualize the structures for GCR, the radiation belts and
338 the solar energetic particles. Values above the scale appear in bright yellow, identical data with extended scale is shown
339 in Figure A 1.

340 3.4. Measurements at low geomagnetic shielding / high latitudes

341 Due to the polar orbit of the Eu:CROPIS satellite, the detector measures at high latitudes and
342 thus at very low, or even negligible, geomagnetic shielding for a fraction of the time. A
343 common quantity to measure the geomagnetic shielding is the effective vertical cut-off rigidity
344 R_C or simply cut-off rigidity (Cooke et al., 1991). The measurements at very low cut-off rigidity
345 can be considered as geomagnetically unshielded. Here, a threshold of $R_C < 0.1 \text{ GV}$ was chosen.
346 This threshold also eliminates most contributions from the inner and outer radiation belt that
347 occur at higher cut-off rigidities or equivalently lower latitudes. This threshold reduces the
348 amount of data to about 5h per day. The values of R_C along the Eu:CROPIS trajectory have
349 been calculated with the PLANETOCOSMICS (Desorgher et al., 2006) application for Geant4
350 (Agostinelli et al., 2003; Allison et al., 2006; Allison et al., 2016) using the International
351 Geomagnetic Reference Field (IGRF-14, (Alken et al., 2021)) in combination with the external
352 magnetic field model by Tsyganenko (1989).

353 Figure 7 summarizes the measurements as one-day-averages at very low geomagnetic
354 shielding. The progression of the solar cycle is clearly visible in the particle flux (Figure 7a)
355 and the dose rate (Figure 7b); the measurements start at high values, approximately $2.5 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$
356 1 and 0.4 mGy/day , during solar activity minimum and GCR intensity maximum and reaching
357 minimum values during solar maximum in 2025, approximately $0.8 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and 0.13 mGy/day .
358 In addition to the continuous measurement of galactic cosmic radiation, sudden spikes in the
359 data show the occurrence of solar energetic particle events. Sometimes, these events are
360 followed by Forbush decreases, temporary decreases in the cosmic ray intensity related to
361 transient interplanetary coronal mass ejections (Cane, 2000; Forbush, 1937) and visible as post-
362 event reductions compared to the pre-event GCR background, e.g. in the second half of 2021.
363 The occurrence probability of SPEs is linked to solar activity, events are far more likely to
364 happen during high solar activity, which is confirmed by the large number of events in 2024
365 and 2025 in Figure 7.

366

367 **Figure 7: One-day-averages of the RAMIS particle flux (a) and absorbed dose rate (b) at very low geomagnetic shielding**
 368 **$R_c < 0.1$ GV (high latitudes).**

369 3.5. Energy deposition spectra, *LET* spectra and dose equivalent

370 The energy deposition measured in the two detectors D1 and D2 of the RAMIS instrument is
 371 stored in a histogram every 5 minutes both for individual hits and for coincidence events. The
 372 angular constraint imposed on particles by the coincidence condition in the telescope limits the
 373 path length through the individual detector and allows the calculation of the linear energy
 374 transfer of particles using the mean path length as described in section 2.2. In this section, a
 375 short summary of the solar energetic particle event in October 2021 is shown as an example
 376 and to demonstrate the capabilities of the detector to measure dose, dose equivalent and quality
 377 factor of cosmic radiation.

378 Figure 8 illustrates the data recorded by RAMIS around the time of the October 2021 solar
 379 energetic particle event at $L > 8$, i.e. at very low geomagnetic shielding (27 Oct and earlier –
 380 prior to the event, 28 Oct – onset of the event, 29 Oct – early phase of the event, 30 Oct and
 381 later – late phase of the event).

382

383 **Figure 8:** a) one-day-averaged energy deposition spectra measured at $L>8$ in the RAMIS D1 detector and b) the
 384 corresponding LET spectra derived from coincidence spectra of RAMIS prior to the solar energetic particle event in
 385 October 2021 (gray line) and during the following days (black lines); c) the differential flux measured in D1 and in
 386 coincidence at $L>8$; d) the one-day-average dose and dose equivalent rate at $L>8$ and the corresponding quality factor
 387 Q .

388 The restriction to $L>8$ reduces the available data to approximately 5h per day but effectively
 389 eliminates contributions from radiation belt particles, c.f. Figure 5. Figure 8a) and b) show the
 390 one-day-averages of the energy deposition spectra and the corresponding converted LET
 391 spectra prior to the event (gray line), during the onset of the event (black solid line) and during
 392 the following two days (black dashed lines). The variations in the shape of the spectra are
 393 caused by impinging protons of different energies. High-energy protons (>1 GeV) are
 394 minimum ionizing particles with a stopping power of ~ 0.2 keV/ μm in water and ~ 0.4 keV/ μm
 395 in silicon corresponding to minimum 0.13 MeV energy deposition in the 300 μm thick detector
 396 for vertically incident particles. For lower energetic protons, the stopping power increases but
 397 a maximum energy deposition in the detector cannot be easily determined due to the changing
 398 stopping power caused by energy loss along the track and the increasing path length at
 399 shallower angles, but it lies in the region between 10 MeV and 20 MeV for stopping protons.
 400 Ergo, the variations in the slope of the spectra can also be understood as changes in the slope
 401 of the primary proton energy spectra during the event: high-energy protons during the onset
 402 and early phase of the event led to increases above the pre-event background also at low energy

403 deposition and LET values while during the later phase of the event, the increase manifests
 404 mostly at higher energy depositions and LET . Figure 8c) shows the evolution of the particle
 405 flux derived from the measured count rates in the single D1 detector (solid black line) and in
 406 coincidence (dashed gray line) using the geometric factors given in Table 1. The geometric
 407 factors are calculated assuming an isotropic irradiation and discrepancies between the resulting
 408 particle flux, as observed prior to the onset of the particle event in Figure 8c), are likely caused
 409 by anisotropies in the radiation field. Such anisotropies can either be inherent in the primary
 410 cosmic radiation field or related to differences in shielding for different incoming angles.
 411 Figure 8d) shows the derived dosimetric quantities, the one-day-average dose (black line), dose
 412 equivalent (red line) and quality factor (blue); the numerical values are given in Table 3. The
 413 quality factor measures the biological effectiveness of ionizing radiation and is defined by the
 414 International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) as a function of LET (ICRP,
 415 1991). The dose rates prior to the solar energetic particle event commencing on the 28 Oct
 416 2021 were about 0.4 mGy/d and 3 mSv/d corresponding to a quality factor of ~ 7 -8. The high
 417 quality factor is a consequence of the dominating contributions from heavy ions in the galactic
 418 cosmic radiation to the dose equivalent. With the onset of the particle event, the dose rates
 419 increased steeply to peak values of 5.50 ± 0.02 mGy/d and 9.6 ± 0.7 mSv/d on the 29 Oct 2021
 420 with a concurrent decrease of the quality factor. The additional dose during the solar particle
 421 event was mostly caused by protons, which have a lower quality factor, typically between 1
 422 and 2. Summing the measured doses between 28 and 31 Oct 2021 and subtracting the pre-event
 423 GCR background yields a total additional dose and dose equivalent from solar energetic
 424 particles of approximately 10 mGy and 14 mSv.

425
 426 **Table 3: One-day-average dose rate d in water, dose equivalent rate h and quality factor Q at $L > 8$ derived from**
 427 **RAMIS D1 and coincidence measurements.**

428

Date	d / (mGy/d)	h / (mSv/d)	Q
2021-10-26	0.41 ± 0.01	3.6 ± 0.6	8.8 ± 1.5
2021-10-27	0.40 ± 0.01	2.8 ± 0.5	6.9 ± 1.3
2021-10-28	3.53 ± 0.02	7.9 ± 0.8	2.2 ± 0.2
2021-10-29	5.50 ± 0.02	9.6 ± 0.7	1.7 ± 0.1
2021-10-30	2.26 ± 0.01	5.8 ± 0.7	2.6 ± 0.3
2021-10-31	0.95 ± 0.01	3.3 ± 0.6	3.4 ± 0.6

429 3.6. Comparison to literature data

430 A detailed comparison to other dosimetric measurements is a complex task, especially
 431 for LEO missions where the radiation belts have a large impact. Such a comparison is outside
 432 the scope of this paper, which is dedicated to give an overview of the RAMIS measurements.
 433 Nevertheless, in this section we will try to put some of the results of the instrument into
 434 perspective with other data.

435 In the first years of the mission, RAMIS measured at almost 600 km altitude during
 436 solar minimum conditions. In May 2020, for instance, the average dose rate was 3655 ± 94
 437 $\mu\text{Gy/day}$ in silicon. Since May 2020 did not show any contributions from the outer radiation
 438 belt (Figure 6a) the measured dose was composed of contributions from SAA and GCR. Using
 439 this data, the contribution from GCR was estimated to be $169 \pm 3 \mu\text{Gy/day}$ in Si which is only
 440 about 5% of the total dose rate. More recently in December 2025 during solar maximum
 441 conditions the average dose rate was $1326 \pm 123 \mu\text{Gy/day}$ in Si with a contribution of around
 442 $72 \pm 3 \mu\text{Gy/day}$ in Si from GCR contribution.

443 The RAMIS data from May 2020 can be compared to data measured inside the ISS at
444 an average altitude of 425 km. The average dose rate measured by the DOSTEL instrument
445 inside the ISS in May 2020 was 285 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{day}$ in Si (Matthiä et al., 2023) with contributions
446 from GCR of 124 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{day}$ and from the crossings of the SAA of 161 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{day}$. The SAA
447 contribution to RAMIS was a factor of 22 higher than inside the ISS, which can be attributed
448 both to the higher altitude and the lower shielding, while the GCR contribution was only 36%
449 higher. Higher values of the average dose rate from GCR can be explained by the high
450 inclination of the satellite compared to ISS, which evades the polar regions where the exposure
451 to GCR is greatest.

452 The LEO-DOS instrument (Nam et al., 2024) on the NEXTSat-2 satellite measured in
453 a similar orbit as RAMIS on Eu:CROPIS. Between July and September 2023 under moderate
454 solar activity, it measured a dose rate in silicon of 4.72 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{h}$ (113.3 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{day}$) from GCR,
455 which is well between the values for solar minimum and maximum from RAMIS.

456 At high geomagnetic latitudes as shown before in Figure 7 RAMIS is in terms of
457 magnetic shielding almost in free space except for the geometric shielding of the Earth which
458 blocks about 30% of the sky at this altitude. The RAMIS GCR dose rates can be extrapolated
459 into free space taking this factor into account. For May 2020 the RAMIS dose rate at $L > 8$ was
460 330 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{day}$ which would result in a dose rate of 472 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{day}$ in Si in free space. This value
461 agrees well with the CRaTER instrument (Spence et al., 2010) which accounted to
462 475 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{day}$ in Si if the CRaTER data (<https://crater.unh.edu>) is recalculated to remove the
463 impact of the Moon shadow.

464

465 4. Summary

466 The RAMIS instrument on the Eu:CROPIS satellite has been measuring the radiation
467 environment in a low Earth polar orbit at altitudes between 500 km and 600 km since
468 December 2018. The sensitive volume of the detector has been covered by 3 mm of aluminium
469 and is sensitive to charged particles from GCR, trapped particles in the inner and outer radiation
470 belts and solar energetic particles above a threshold of 24.3 MeV for protons and 1.38 MeV for
471 electrons. Due to the much higher energies of GCR, these thresholds are relevant only for
472 radiation belt and solar energetic particles. The one-minute time resolution of the dose rate and
473 particle flux data allows an accurate parameterization of the data with geomagnetic shielding
474 expressed by the cut-off rigidity R_c and the magnetic field parameter L . To date, RAMIS has
475 collected data for more than seven years with a coverage of 92%. It has recorded the variation
476 of the GCR intensity during the solar activity cycle from solar minimum in the early 2020s to
477 the current solar maximum with a decrease of the particle flux from around $2.5 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ to
478 $0.8 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ at high latitudes and a concurrent decrease of the dose rate from 0.4 mGy/d to
479 0.13 mGy/d. During this time, the instrument has also recorded a number of solar energetic
480 particle events, the largest showing peak flux rates of several tens of particles per cm^2 and
481 second and dose rates of several mGy/d at high latitudes.

482 The telescope geometry of RAMIS and the coincidence measurements allow the
483 estimation of the linear energy spectrum and the calculation of the quality factor in a 5-minute
484 cadence. The quality factor can be applied to the measured dose rate to estimate the dose
485 equivalent rate, which is relevant for radiation protection. Variations in the composition of the
486 radiation field can be observed as variations in the quality factor. If dose rates are dominated
487 by GCR, the quality factor can reach values of 9, caused by contributions from heavy ions,
488 while proton-rich environments have a much lower quality factor. This was illustrated for the
489 development of the measured dose and dose equivalent rates during the solar energetic particle
490 event in October 2021.

491 In future work, a more detailed analysis, e.g. based on a cut-off rigidity or L based
492 parameterization, may allow also the application of the quality factor to the one-minute data.
493 The data provided by RAMIS may also be used to perform more detailed investigations of
494 individual solar energetic particle events or times of high outer radiation belt activity. The
495 RAMIS instrument is currently still operating and continues to provide data.
496

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506 Data Availability Statement

507 The data used in this manuscript is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19354133>.

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691 **Annex A**

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Figure A 1: Identical data as in Figure 6 but with extended scale. Visualization of the geographical distribution of one-month-average particle fluence rates of different particle populations measured by RAMIS during solar quiet

696 times in May 2020 (a), including a solar energetic particle event in October 2021 (b) and the formation of a high-
697 energy and high-intensity component in the outer radiation belt in November 2021 (c).

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